

Chemical Examination of the seeds of *Litsea consimilis*: Part II: Studies on the Unsaponifiable Matter

D. R. Gupta* and S. K. Garg**

β -sitosterol has been isolated from the unsaponifiable matter of the oil from the seeds of *Litsea consimilis*, and has been identified by its physical and chemical properties and by the preparation of its acetate, benzoate and digitonide derivatives. Further confirmation of its identity has been established by its mixed chromatogram with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol over a column of Brockmann alumina.

Amongst lauraceae plants, the seed and fruit coat fats of cinnamomum, *Litsea* and related genera have been investigated by a number of workers¹⁻⁴. *Litsea consimilis*, a species of *Litsea*, grows plentifully in Kumaon region. The oil from its berries is used by the local people in the treatment of various skin diseases and is applied for healing wounds. This plant has not been investigated so far. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to take up a systematic study of this plant. The amino acid make-up of proteins isolated from the seeds and the analysis of the seed fat and fruit coat fat of *Litsea consimilis* were reported earlier^{5,7}. In the present communication, the authors have reported the isolation and characterization of β -sitosterol from the unsaponifiable matter of the oil from the seeds of this plant.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation and purification of the sterol : Dry seeds of *Litsea consimilis* were powdered and Soxhletted with petroleum ether (B.P. 60-80°). The oil obtained after removal of petroleum ether was purified by treating it with Fuller's earth and activated charcoal, and freed from volatile essential oil as far as possible by heating in *vacuo*. It was saponified by refluxing on water bath for 12 hr. with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution. After saponification, the product was diluted with water and the alcohol distilled off on water bath with the addition of corresponding amount of water from time to time. The alcohol free aqueous solution of soap was extracted several times with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over fused calcium chloride and the solvent distilled off, when a crude brown semisolid residue of the sterol was obtained.

The crude sterol was refluxed with methanol for 6 hours and kept for 20 hr. in a refrigerator; the process was repeated twice when the precipitate of the crude sterol (2.6%; unsaponifiable matter) was obtained. The crude precipitate of the sterol was thoroughly dried in a vacuum desiccator; m.p. 130-135°.

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*Present address: Department of Chemistry, S.B.S. and H. U. P. Agricultural University, Pant'nagar.

**Department of Pharmacology, Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh.

The crude sterol was dissolved in minimum quantity of benzene and was chromatographed over a column of Brockmann alumina (35 cm. \times 1.5 cm.) and eluted with various solvents and their mixtures. Eluents were collected in fractions of 35 ml. each as shown in the following table :

Fractions	Eluents	Residue on evaporation of solvent
1-6	Petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°)	Oily mass
7-10	Petroleum ether+ Benzene (3:2 v/v)	Oily mass
11-14	Petroleum ether+ Benzene (1:1 v/v)	Nil
15-18	Benzene	Nil
19-25	Benzene+ Chloroform (3:2 (v/v)	Shining flakes
26-30	Benzene+ Chloroform (1:1 v/v)	Shining flakes
31-34	Chloroform	Nil
35-38	Methanol+ Chloroform (1:99 v/v)	Nil

Fractions 19-30, containing the sterol in the form of shining flakes, were combined and on repeated crystallisations from a mixture of methanol and ethyl acetate (1:1 v/v) yielded colourless flakes with constant m. p. 136-137°. The sterol was fairly soluble in benzene, methanol and ethanol and readily soluble in chloroform, ether and ethyl acetate. The compound developed a green colour in the Liebermann-Buchard test, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -36.5^\circ$ in chloroform). It did not depress the m. p. of an authentic sample of β -sitosterol (Found: C, 83.70; H, 12.21; $C_{29}H_{50}O$ requires C, 84.05; H, 12.08%).

*Acetyl derivative of the sterol*⁸: The sterol (0.1 gm.) was treated with acetic anhydride (1.0 ml) and 2 drops of pyridine. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature and then treated for about 6 hrs. on water bath. The reaction mixture was poured to crushed ice and kept in the refrigerator overnight. The solid was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised several times from a mixture of methanol and acetone (1 : 1 v/v) in colourless flakes, m. p. 126°, yield, 0.051 gms.

*Benzoyl derivative of the sterol*⁸: The sterol (0.1 gm.) was treated with benzoyl chloride (1.0 ml.) and 2 drops of pyridine. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature and then heated for about 6 hrs. on water bath. The mixture was poured into ice-cold water and kept in the refrigerator overnight. The solid was filtered off, washed with 2% aqueous KOH (till free from benzoic acid) and then with water and finally crystallised from a mixture of methanol and acetone (1 : 1 v/v), m. p. 144°, yield, 0.04 gms.

*Digitonide derivative of the sterol*⁹: A saturated solution of the sterol (0.1 gm.) in absolute alcohol at 60° was heated with an equal volume of a saturated solution of digitonin in 95% alcohol. The mixture was refluxed on water bath for about 2 hr. and then kept at 0° for 12 hr. in the refrigerator, when the digitonide was obtained as a white powder, m. p. 230°, yield, 0.05 gms.

*Mixed chromatogram of the sterol with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol*¹⁰: The sterol (0.04 gm) with an equal quantity of an authentic sample of β -sitosterol was dissolved in minimum quantity of benzene and chromatographed over a column of Brockmann alumina

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(15×0.5 cm.). Elution with benzene and a mixture of benzene and chloroform (1:1 v/v) yielded from the first six fractions 0.070 gms. of a solid, which on crystallisation from a mixture of methanol and ethyl acetate (1:1 v/v) furnished colourless flakes with constant m.p. 137°.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF ROORKEE,
ROORKEE, INDIA.

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